

NOTES

Complexes of *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-(pyrid-2-yl)-thiocarbamide with Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

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TRANSITION metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands have been studied extensively¹. As a part of our studies, we report here a few complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Benzoyl isothiocyanate was prepared by the method reported earlier². A mixture of equimolar amounts of 2-aminopyridine in acetone and benzoyl isothiocyanate was refluxed for 4–5 h. The solution was then poured in ice-cold water and the syrupy liquid formed was kept overnight. The resulting yellowish white crystals of *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide. It was washed with acetone, recrystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were prepared by adding acetone solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) slowly to a hot solution of the metal ion (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The solution was refluxed for 3 h and then the solvent was allowed to evaporate upto 50% of the volume. The Cu^{II} complex was formed immediately after evaporation. The complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} were precipitated after the concentrated solution was kept in ice-cold water for a few minutes.

The complexes were found to be insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform, acetone and benzene. The structures of the complexes were determined by elemental analysis, magnetic moment, molar conductance (DMF), infrared (KBr) and electronic spectral data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show the metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 2 for all the complexes. Low molar conductance values (60–100 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Most of the complexes melt above 200°. The molecular weight measurement (Rast's camphor method) indicate that all the complexes are monomeric in nature.

The characteristic ir band in the spectra of the ligand is a broad and strong band at 3 400–3 000 cm^{-1} which represents a series of overlapping stretching vibrations corresponding to NH groups. The CH stretching vibration of aromatic ring seems to have been enveloped with the NH band. The position of the band remains practically unaltered in the complexes implying non-coordination of the thiomide nitrogen atoms to the metal ions³. The band at $\sim 1 670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O) in the ligand did not shift to lower frequency region in the complexes, which indicates that carbonyl oxygen atom is not involved in the bonding. The band at 1 570 cm^{-1} (C=N) in the ligand shifted to lower frequency region and observed at $\sim 1 540 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes indicating the coordination of pyridyl-*N*⁴ with the metal ion. The band at $\sim 1 250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S)⁵ in the ligand shifted to lower frequency region in all the metal complexes and observed at 1 180 cm^{-1} , which indicates the involvement of thiocarbonyl sulphur atom in the bonding. The bands at 740 and 720 cm^{-1} (C=S)⁷ shifted to slightly higher frequency in the metal complexes due to the sulphur–metal coordination bond formation¹. Additional bands appears in the nitrate complexes at 1 500, 1 300, 1 020 and 930 cm^{-1} , and that in the perchlorate complexes at 1 260, 1 130 and 1 000 cm^{-1} . These bands unambiguously suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate⁸ and perchlorate group⁹. The coordination through nitrogen atom is also confirmed by occurrence of new bands at 470–460 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes which are assigned to M–N stretching vibration¹⁰. If the thiomide nitrogen and sulphur act as donors, a four-membered chelate ring would be formed which is quite unstable in comparison to the six-membered chelate ring formed by the coordination of nitrogen of pyridine ring and thiocarbonyl sulphur. On the basis of ir spectra and magnetic moment values the following structure is proposed.

where, X = Cl, Br, NO₃ and ClO₄.

The μ_{eff} values of the Cu^{II} complexes lie in the range 1.67–1.90 B.M. which does not involve spin-spin interaction¹¹. The Ni^{II} complexes

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			M	N	S	Cl/Br
BPTC	Yellowish white	—	—	16.26 (16.34)	12.4 (12.5)	—
Cu(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Steel grey	1.67	9.19 (9.28)	12.12 (12.27)	9.21 (9.34)	10.26 (10.37)
Cu(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Grey	1.69	8.50 (8.61)	11.31 (11.38)	8.51 (8.67)	21.57 (21.69)
Cu(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Green	1.84	8.32 (8.40)	18.40 (18.52)	8.32 (8.47)	—
Cu(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Greenish yellow	1.90	7.09 (7.18)	9.23 (9.49)	7.10 (7.23)	7.91 (8.03)
Co(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Bluish white	4.50	7.64 (7.88)	11.01 (11.17)	8.34 (8.51)	9.23 (9.44)
Co(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Faint blue	4.57	8.10 (8.24)	11.52 (11.74)	8.63 (8.95)	22.12 (22.38)
Co(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Olive green	4.70	8.30 (8.45)	16.00 (16.07)	9.00 (9.18)	—
Co(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Dark yellow	4.75	7.50 (7.63)	10.62 (10.83)	8.10 (8.29)	9.00 (9.19)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Canary yellow	2.98	8.90 (9.13)	12.92 (13.06)	9.61 (9.95)	10.90 (11.04)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Brown	2.99	6.90 (7.04)	9.80 (10.08)	7.41 (7.68)	19.10 (19.21)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Pale violet	3.10	7.10 (7.29)	13.7 (13.91)	7.63 (7.95)	—
Ni(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Violet	3.30	6.50 (6.70)	9.50 (9.60)	7.21 (7.34)	8.00 (8.14)

*BPTC = C₁₁H₁₁ON₂S.

having values in the range 2.98–3.3 B.M. is indicative of octahedral structure. The Co^{II} complexes have values in the range 4.5–4.75 B.M. which can also be assigned to octahedral structure. The complexes of Cu^{II} show a broad band around 14 280 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the transition, ²E_g → ²T_{2g}. Besides, a band around 25 000 cm⁻¹ exists which may be due to charge transfer band. The complexes of Co^{II} exhibit two bands at 9 100 and 18 900 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the transitions, ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₂) respectively, in an approximately octahedral field^{1,2}. A charge transfer band is also observed at 27 000 cm⁻¹. The complexes of Ni^{II} exhibit three well-resolved bands at 9 800, 16 400 and 25 800 cm⁻¹ attributed to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions respectively under an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion^{1,2}.

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Studies on the Stability of some Binary and Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

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BINARY complexes of some bivalent metal ions with oxydiacetic acid (ODAA) have been reported¹⁻⁴. A survey of the literature has revealed that mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with ODAA as primary ligand, and maleic acid (MALEA), malonic acid (MALNA) and phthalic acid (PHA) as secondary ligands have not been studied so far. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to determine the formation constants of binary and ternary complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with the above ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The pH-titrations were carried out at 25 ± 0.5° using